

An investigation into difficulties of listening skills of freshmen at English language faculty.

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Abstract

In fact, English is popular not only in Vietnam but also in many countries around the world. But not everyone can learn this language well, people have to go through a learning process from Elementary or Junior High to High School and even college. In this language, not only does it requires students to study hard, but it also requires students to be highly gifted and focused. English is divided into four skills that support each other. In particular, listening skills are the key skills in all. The problem is that not all students realize the importance of listening skills, they often ignore it and then they cannot communicate with foreigner (Gilakjani, 2016). This investigation helps students realize the importance and difficult of listening, helping students reinforce their ability to listen more and more completely.

Keywords: listening, realize, difficult, communicate.

1. Introduction

As an international language, English is spoken in most countries in the world, being the second language in every country including Vietnam. English is divided into four skills, which are listening, speaking, reading and writing. Listening is a skill that compels students to be the most proficient because without listening skills the communication process cannot work well (**Abbas Pourhosein Gilakjani, 2016**). For foreign language learning, listening is an indispensable skill, it provides the language input (Renukadevi, 2014). As for that, listening plays an important role in everyday communication. In this study, the author focuses on freshmen' listening problems, according to a university survey on the importance of skills. The result showed that listening skills account for 45% of person's communication time, more than speaking (accounts for 30%), reading and writing (accounts for 16% and 9% respectively). Nevertheless, many students (even teachers) often do not spend a lot time on attention to the listening skills. This leads to the fact that learners often say that listening is one of the most difficult skills, especially, freshman in English major (Dan, 2018). Why is listening skill a weakness of freshman at English language faculty? This is project is an attempt to identify problems faced by freshmen at Ho Chi Minh City University of Food Industry.

By identifying the problems, this study helps freshmen create their own strategies for developing their listening skills in a more complete (**Al-Nafisah, 2019**). In addition, at also contributes to raise student' awareness of this skill.

5. Literature review

5.1. Definition of listening skill.

Listening is the ability to receive and explain messages in the communication process. Besides, listening is the key of communication, listening severs some of possible purposes; it directly

supports other skills such as writing, speaking. For example, having a problem at work or study that instead of listening closely to what they are saying, we often forget about some sentences that lead to misunderstandings because of distracted psychology or not really good listening skills. According to Krashen (1985) and Hamouda (2013) "listening skill is an important element in obtaining understandable input" (Hamouda, 2013). Listening requires learners to have a solid knowledge of vocabulary and ability to pronounce correctly. Especially, listening is an interaction between listeners and speakers or listeners and writers, it is one of a necessary skill that learners have to acquire in learning

5.2. The important of listening English.

Listening is a skill that help learners develop their language perception. Although this is a very difficult skill, it is also a beneficial skill for learning English, helping learners improve their pronunciation and communication skills in English. In using language, listening skills play an integral part, this skill determines the understanding, content and attitude of the speakers with the listeners. Unfortunately, listening skills are considered to be a passive skill, in the class, learners are often silent and not focused listening, they think rambling and ignore this skill until they completely lose listening skills. It is often more demanding than other skills, which require more time, so its importance is also superior to other skills. Most freshmen are weak at listening English (including English-majored students) because the mistake of them is that they only focus on other skills as writing, reading, speaking than listening skills. It is suggested that listening is considered to be an increasingly relevant language skill, emphasizing the need for this skill, thereby devising appropriate strategies to develop it (A.H.Al-Jamal, 2019).

If learners do not understand what they listen and what they say in their classroom, they may have serious effects, leading to problems in speaking and writing. (Zhang, 2013) . It seems that learners are always scared if they do not have listening skill, that is the reason why they are unbalanced in communication. Some suggested that learners need to practice the habit of listening to English by different people to get closer to reality by talking a lot with foreigners, watching many movies and listening to English music, etc...

5.3. Difficulties in listening.

Listening is a skill that requires significant training and a high level of focus on the subject matter. Becoming a good learner of listening goes through stages and has a high level of thinking in other sub-skills. Listening is a complex process, it requires interdependence between skills (Ozgur Celik, 2015). She commented that listening is not simply hearing, it needs to be attentive to the message of what is said, the meaning and to want to do that, the learners must complete 3 levels: message, grammar, vocabulary and lastly the sound system.

When asked about the reason for the difficulty with sounds in English, some people think that this difficulty is because they cannot distinguish English sounds, homophones, especially words that have almost identical pronunciation. In particular, the confusion between positive and negative forms is the main reason, especially the failure to recognize the main information to listen because of some characteristics of pronounce in the language like the phenomenon of swallowing (elision), the weak form in pronouncing some functional words (weak form), the phenomenon of phonemic assimilation (assimilation), the phenomenon of shortening of the word (contraction), the phenomenon of sound coupling (linking)....

Thus, the learners do not recognize the sounds in English mainly because: cannot distinguish homophones and words with similar pronunciation, confuse affirmative and negative form. Besides, listening is the most stressful subjects because it is limited in time, information comes from unclear or effected by the surrounding environment. In some schools, listening skills are limited because of the lack of clear sound equipment and distracting noise, etc... learners often lack the motivation to focus on the topic, feeling anxious to listen or contribute to a debate, distracted by content of another story. In addition, a lack of knowledge about the topic can lead to wrong listening. For Vietnamese, learners face to linguistic challenges and cultural strangeness.

5.4. The roles of listening skill development.

According to Dr. David J. Mendelsohn from the Faculty of linguistics, literature and linguistics, York University, he pointed out that total amount of time spent communicating and listening accounts for 40-50%, speaking 25-30%, reading from 11-16% and time spent on writing only 9% (**Abbas Pourhossein Gilakjani, 2011**). So learning any language by spending time listening, listening a lot, absorbing a lot of language is a right strategy. English is no exception. Dr. Hossein Bozorgian, in his doctoral dissertation, surveying more than 700 students preparing for the IELTS exam showed that research has confirmed that listening skill are strongly correlated with general language proficiency. Listening skills are fundamental to language absorption. When listening well in English, learners will have a great advantage in acquiring information quickly, interestingly, talking advantage of the free time. Whoever you are, in any profession, just good listening English you can get access to high quality knowledge from the internet. Compared to reading, learning through audio and visual will be much more intuitive, interesting and vivid.

5.5. Listening skills of freshmen.

There are many reasons why learners find it difficult to learn to listen, one of the basic reasons is that listening skills are not focused in the process of learning English in junior high school or high school. Freshmen majoring in English language faculty at Ho Chi Minh City University of Food Industry also face difficulties in listening to listen. Through the survey as well as the last grade, the English midterm and final listening skills tests are lower than the speaking, reading and writing skills.

Some of the freshmen think that they make mistakes in listening, listening inaccuracies which makes their scores lower even if they have to repeat the listening subject. Through interviews, the reason why freshmen lack of motivation to learn listening at school and home are some teachers use the source of listening materials in the textbook or certain reference books to build the exam questions. So some of freshmen used the rote skill before the exam. Due to poor awareness of the importance of listening to listen, freshmen lacked time to invest in listening. These two factors directly affect the listening skill of freshmen. Indeed, if not invested a lot of time, the freshmen will not have a reaction to listening and will not keep up with speed of the speakers and the ability to listen will be increasingly deteriorated. One of the other causes is the inability to know what to start and how to use it effectively.

5.6. Problems that the learners face with listening.

5.6.1. Quality of recorded.

In some schools, using some recorded materials that do not have high quality. The quality of sound systems can impact the learners' listening.

5.6.2. Accents.

The speaker's voice is one of the important factors affecting the listeners. Even native speakers can cause this problem. In addition, in some countries using English but complete different accents will interrupt the listening process.

5.6.3. Cultural differences.

Cultural is unique to each other country so it has a great influence on the language. Cultural issues and requires learners to clearly understand the culture to avoid interrelated social issues. The teacher is responsible for providing relevant materials before students.

5.6.4. Homophones.

In English, some words that sound similar to another word, but different from that in the meaning or spellings are called homonyms. Giving an example, "sea" /si:/ or "see" /si:/, both are similar in pronunciation but different in meaning, which can lead to students misunderstanding the meaning of the speaker.

5.7. Resources to learn listening skills.

According to Feyisa Demie (2013) "English as an additional language pupil", on average, a child takes an average of 1.5 years from the ignorant period about English to get used to English, then it takes another 3 years to confidently use English and takes another 2.5 years to be called fully fluent in English. In total, the whole process takes about 6 years to fully masters English. So do not worry, be calm and listen to advice from language expert. Lindsay and Knight have listed all the sources learners can listen and emphasizes that they are diverse (**Helen Timperley, 2007**). Mr. Helgesen agrees with two authors. He offers some sources such as teacher-student conversations, news, magazines, songs, etc...

6. Method

Research at Ho Chi Minh city university of food industry. The object of the research is freshmen about listening skills in English. The research highlights the current situation of the process of listening and resolving these issues and devise new techniques to carry out improving listening skills of students.

6.1. Research design.

A quantitative has been used for the study. This method requires a survey of 40 English-majored freshmen at HUFU. To observe and interview students to complete the data.

6.2. Measures

Having 6 principles for effective listening skills.

6.2.1. Focus on the communication.

Communication is a two-way interaction, listeners should focus on absorbing what the opponent is conveying, limiting distractions such as: turning off the phone, finding peace space...

6.2.2. Listen to what learners like.

The solution to making things learners love and listen to English is to combine together. Listening to English with favorite topics will make it easy, enjoyable, inspiring to learn, which is a necessary condition for learners to keep up their daily listening habits in English.

6.2.3. Choosing the content of listening to suit of ability.

It sounds good to hear a lot, but the content is too hard, the subject is too intensive, the listening will stop at the level of being familiar with the sounds, of course this does not help listeners have any knowledge at all. In order to be able to choose suitable listening content, it is necessary to know where your current level is. The most common and common English assessment standard is according to the Common European Framework of Reference (CEFR). Under this framework, English proficiency is divided into 6 levels from low to high including: A1, A2, B1, B2, C1, C2.

+ A1: break-through

+A2: way stage

+B1: threshold

+B2: vantage

+C1: effective proficiency

+C3: mastery

6.2.4. Listen, read and repeat.

This is one of the extremely affective techniques that any good English person knows and applies to their lives. when listening to something, try to listen without translating into Vietnamese mastering the gist and then learners are listening and rereading, the brain associates the audible sound of the word with the character of the word. This process helps learners know words, learn new words in the form of audio and gradually convert many passive words slowly into active vocabulary.

6.2.5. Guess the main idea.

To be able to hear well, the first guess what is about to be heard, the purpose is to make the necessary mental preparation and vocabulary. When there is not enough data to hear the main idea, students need to guess one or the main ideas based on what they have heard. This helps

them have the necessary comparison, if the student's guess is right, the more they hear they will find supportive arguments. However, this method is not 100% correct, it will still be risky.

6.2.6. Listen to English every day and continuously.

There is no shortcut here, only effort, perseverance, determination. Trying to turn English listening into an indispensable habit like brushing your teeth, washing your face, showering every day. Learners set announcements and register pages that they can listen to English immediately such as YouTube, CNN videos, BBC news... listening wherever you are, wherever you have free time, making listening to English a daily task is indispensable, which is the general secret of good English learners.

6.3. Research finding.

6.3.1. Participants subject.

The subjects of this study focused on learning about the difficulties in freshmen and methods students used to improve listening. In addition, several reasons for freshmen' ineffective listening learning were also included in this study. Participants of the study include 40 freshmen of English major.

6.3.2. Questionnaires.

1. what was the number of marks you took on the previous semester's listening test?

A: > 5 marks

B: 5 marks

C: < 5 marks

2. How do you feel about the listening skills with other skills (reading, speaking, writing)?

A: Very hard

B: Hard

C: Normal

D: Easy

E: Very easy

3. How often do you self-study listening at home?

A: Never.

B: sometimes

C: often

4. What do you do if you cannot understand words in paragraphs while listening?

A: try to guess its meaning.

B: disappointed and do not want to listen anymore

C: do not worry and keep on listening.

5. Which of this following problems do you often encounter?

A: Prediction what the speaker will talk about.

B: Lacking of knowledge.

C: Different accents

D: Long listening test

E: The sound system is too bad

F: Noises

G: Poor vocabulary

H: Hesitation

I: The speaker talks to fast

6: freshmen give some ideas (collect ideas from 5 freshmen and choose 40 freshmen to vote on these ideas)

6.3.3. Procedure.

Step 1: Giving freshmen the questionnaire and explain to them how to understand all the technical terms in the questionnaire.

Step 2: Make sure the participants will answer the questionnaire seriously.

Step 3: After the data have been collected, remove the data that is inaccurate.

Step 4: Calculate

7. Results and discussion.

Diagram1: Survey the listening test marks of freshmen in the previous semester.

In the first section of the questionnaire, freshmen are required to give a listening test score for the previous semester. The chart above shows that 53,7% of freshmen are under five marks and only 15,5 of freshmen are above five marks. This problem is the general situation of most freshmen at HUFU.

Table 1: Assessment of student' listening skills.

Assessment	Very hard	Hard	Normal	Easy	Very easy
% (choice)	16/40 (40%)	22/40 (55%)	2/40 (5%)	0	0

From the assessment above, it can see that freshmen find that listening skills are always a difficult skill and they always face many challenges when learning this skill. It can say that listening skill is the most difficult skill of language.

Table 2: freshmen' perceptions are related to their high school education.

Statements	Total students	Excellent	Good	Fair	Poor	Very poor
Reading	40	4,44%	72,1%	16,8%	3,33%	3,33%
Listening	40	0,00%	10,5%	45,8%	43,7%	0%
Speaking	40	2,5%	40,7%	30,9%	23,6%	2,3%

In the second table of the questionnaire, freshmen are required to assess their perceptions of teaching skills at high education institutions. According to them, they satisfy with how to teach writing, reading and speaking skills (6,7%, 4,44%,2,5% respectively) and they all thought that listening skill was the most difficult (0,00%), most freshmen rated the listening skills as fair and poor.

Table 3: Which of this following problems do you often encounter?

problems	never	sometimes	often	always
Prediction what the speaker will talk a		32%	24,5%	43,5%
Lacking of knowledge.	10,2%	30,8%	59%	
Different accents		23,7%	47,6%	28,7%
Long listening test	15,8%	20,4%	31,2%	32,6%
The sound system is too bad		47,2%	33,6%	19,2%
noises		32,4%	41,1%	26,5%
Poor vocabulary		47,8%	38,3%	13,9%
Hesitation	18,6%	47,3%	34,1%	
The speaker talks to fast	5,8%	48,3%	29,1%	16,8%

This is statistic about problems that freshmen often make mistakes in a listening session. From the above statistics, it is shown that lack of knowledge in listening is a problem for almost all freshmen, accounting for 59% (often), followed by a variety of accents that also make it difficult for them hear basically freshmen do not have much contact with many different accents. The result from table 3 show that 47,6% and 32,6% of freshmen met this problem. For example, if an Indian or Korean speaks English, freshmen often find it difficult to understand when they speak because they often speak English in their own country intonation. Especially with some freshmen exposed to standard British or American accents, they will have trouble understanding other accents. YaGang affirms that listeners tend to get used to the accents they mostly listen to (Hamouda, 2013).

Besides, the speaker also seriously affects freshmen' hearing ability, most of them speak very fast, swallow many words, causing the listener may lose many keywords. 48,3% of freshmen said that they sometimes could not hear what the speaker was saying that makes them distracting, embarrassing and seemingly unable to do test. Moreover, long listening tests make freshmen feel tired, with 63,8% (often and always) freshmen find that long listening is a big obstacle. In fact, freshmen listen to an essay for a long time, they feel pressured. A long listening session requires them to have a good memory and quick note-taking ability. However, both of these issues are not easy for freshmen, even many freshmen fall asleep in the listening and this is not effective. In addition, factors such as noise and poor sound system are also causes of freshmen' listening skills become weak.

Beside, freshmen also raise other problems. Here are five problems raised by freshmen and received a lot of positive support.

Table 4: top five listening' problem

No	Rank	Category	Statements	Percentage
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			(%)
1	1	Lack of concentration	87,6%
2	2	speaker	74,5%
3	3	Listening Material	72,3%
4	4	psychology	54,8%
5	5	Physical settings	51,5%

These problems are recommended by freshmen and voted by 40 freshmen at HUFU. This table shows that Lack of concentration has the highest percentage (87,6%), freshmen think they are distracted by many problems that is why they fail the listening tests. A large number of freshmen think that they cannot concentrate because of the noise around them. According to Hamouda, noises are environmental barrier affecting listening comprehension.

The second is the speaker (Hamouda, 2013). Speaker have an important impact on freshmen' listening. At school, the audio was played on CD so the sound is un-clear.

The third is listening material. Freshmen tend to memorize what they have learnt, they depend too much on the material and they will not be able to hear if the content of the text is unfamiliar to them. the 4th position which "Freshmen feel disappointed if they do not understand the content". This problem will be more serious if the listening test contains many strange words and complex structures, they will give up and be depressed.

The last is physical setting. It is difficult to hear in environments that contains lot of noise. Noise is included in the classroom and outside, which can cause freshmen to give up thinking about the content of listening test.

8. Conclusions.

According to this study, the biggest difficulty for freshmen when listening skills at home and school are the lack of knowledge and motivation, freshmen do not invest much time in learning to listen. Therefore, raising awareness about the important role of listening skills in learning and communication needs to be emphasized by teachers. In addition to changing the mechanism, policies, setting questions, talking examinations, diversifying listening sources while making listening test questions is also a necessity for them to be more active in learning to listen.

The second, poor equipment quality, lack of concentration, un-clear pronunciation and unfamiliar topics are a concern of many freshmen. This study points out the factors that cause some serious for listeners and provides some helpful hints for freshmen.

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